

BIR O‘LCHAMLI PANJARADAGI SHREODINGER OPERATORINING XOS QIYMATLARI SONI VA JOYLASHGAN O‘RNI

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Annotatsiya: Bir o‘lchamli panjarada Shreodinger operatorining o‘zaro ta’sir parametrlariga bog‘liq holda uning muhim spektridan quyida hamda yuqorida yakkalangan xos qiymatlarining mavjudligi isbotlanadi.

Kalit so‘zlar: Shreodinger opeartori, panjara, spektr, tor, Hilbert fazosi, xos qiymat.

$\mathbb{T} = (-\pi, \pi]$ bir o‘lchamli tor bo‘lsin. $L^2(\mathbb{T})$ esa torda kvadrati bilan integrallanuvchi funksiyalar Hilbert fazosi bo‘lsin.

Bir zarrachali Shreodinger operatori $H_{\gamma\lambda}$, $L^2(\mathbb{T})$ Hilbert fazosida quyidagicha aniqlangan:

$$H_{\gamma\lambda} = H_0 - V_{\gamma\lambda}, \gamma, \lambda \in \mathbb{R}.$$

Bu yerda

$$[H_0 f](q) = \varepsilon(q)f(q), \quad \varepsilon(q) = 2(1 - \cos 2q), \quad f \in L^2(\mathbb{T}),$$

$$[V_{\gamma\lambda} f](p) = \frac{\gamma}{2\pi} \int_{\mathbb{T}} f(q) dq + \frac{\lambda}{\pi} \cos p \int_{\mathbb{T}} \cos q f(q) dq + \\ + \frac{\lambda}{\pi} \sin p \int_{\mathbb{T}} \sin q f(q) dq, \quad f \in L^2(\mathbb{T}).$$

H_0 operator uzluksiz haqiqiy qiymatli funksiyaga ko‘paytirish operatori bo‘lgani uchun

$$\sigma(H_0) = \sigma_{\text{ess}}(H_0) = [\varepsilon_{\min}, \varepsilon_{\max}],$$

bu yerda

$$\varepsilon_{\min} = 0, \quad \varepsilon_{\max} = 4.$$

$V_{\gamma\lambda}$ operatori chekli rangli bo‘lgani sababli Weyl teoremasiga [1] ko‘ra

$$\sigma_{\text{ess}}(H_{\gamma\lambda}) = \sigma_{\text{ess}}(H_0).$$

$L^{2,e}(\mathbb{T})$ va $L^{2,o}(\mathbb{T})$ orqali $L^2(\mathbb{T})$ Hilbert fazosining mos ravishda juft va toq funksiyalardan iborat qism fazolarini belgilaymiz:

$$L^{2,e}(\mathbb{T}) = \{f \in L^2(\mathbb{T}): f(p) = f(-p), \quad p \in \mathbb{T}\},$$

$$L^{2,o}(\mathbb{T}) = \{f \in L^2(\mathbb{T}): f(p) = -f(-p), \quad p \in \mathbb{T}\}.$$

U holda

$$L^2(\mathbb{T}) = L^{2,e}(\mathbb{T}) \oplus L^{2,o}(\mathbb{T}).$$

H_0 operatori juft $\varepsilon(p) = 2 - 2\cos 2p$ funksiyaga ko'paytirish operatori bo'lgani uchun, har bir $\theta \in \{e, o\}$ uchun $L^{2,\theta}(\mathbb{T})$ qismfazosi H_0 ga nisbatan invariantdir.

$V_{\gamma\lambda}$ operatorining ko'rinishidan kelib chiqib, uning juft va toq qism fazolardagi ko'rinishlarini mos ravishda $V_{\gamma\lambda}^e$ va V_{λ}^o orqali belgilasak, quyidagilarga ega bo'lamiz:

$$(V_{\gamma\lambda}^e f)(p) = \frac{\gamma}{2\pi} \int_{\mathbb{T}} f(q) dq + \frac{\lambda}{\pi} \cos p \int_{\mathbb{T}} \cos qf(q) dq, f \in L^{2,e}(\mathbb{T}),$$

$$(V_{\lambda}^o f)(p) = \frac{\lambda}{\pi} \sin p \int_{\mathbb{T}} \sin qf(q) dq, f \in L^{2,o}(\mathbb{T}).$$

Yuqoridagilardan $H_{\gamma\lambda}$ operatorning qism fazolardagi ko'rinishlari quyidagicha hosil bo'ladi:

$$H_{\gamma\lambda}^e := H_0 + V_{\gamma\lambda}^e,$$

$$H_{\lambda}^o := H_0 + V_{\lambda}^o.$$

Natijada spektr quyidagicha ajraladi:

$$\sigma(H_{\gamma\lambda}) = \sigma(H_{\gamma\lambda}^e) \cup \sigma(H_{\lambda}^o).$$

Teorema 1. Faraz qilaylik, $z \in \mathbb{C}$, $z \notin [0,4]$ bo'lsin.

1. Agar $\lambda > 0$ bo'lsa, u holda H_{λ}^o operator muhim spektrdan yuqorida yagona xos qiymatga ega.
2. Agar $\lambda < 0$ bo'lsa, u holda H_{λ}^o operator muhim spektrdan yuqorida xos qiymatga ega emas.
3. Agar $\lambda < -2$ bo'lsa, u holda H_{λ}^o operator muhim spektrdan quyida yagona xos qiymatga ega.
4. Agar $\lambda > -2$ bo'lsa, u holda H_{λ}^o operator muhim spektrdan quyida xos qiymatga ega emas.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati

1. **M.Reed, B.Simon** *Methods of modern mathematical physics. IV: Analysis of Operators*. T.: Academic Press, New York. - 1979.